

highly susceptible. Satha D, Akashi, Bagri, and N22 were most susceptible. Bagri Black, Bagri White, Bhadaila kala, Budhi, Gorakhpur local, Kudia,

Lalmati-A, Lurkan, Miriti, Kachni, Rani Kajal, Satha-F, and Sarya had moderate infection.

In farmers' fields, severe leaf B1

was observed on popular indigenous varieties Lalmati, Mutmuri, N22, Mutmuriya, and Bagri. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Screening rice varieties for cold tolerance at seedling and reproductive stages

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Cold tolerance at the seedling stage as well as at the reproductive stage is essential for early dry season rice in West Bengal. We screened a number of newly developed lines and three hill varieties in 1984-85 to identify genotypes possessing both characters.

Seeds were sown 21 Nov 1984. Leaf

yellowing and plant height were scored at 25, 45, and 55 d after sowing (DAS). Two new lines ES1-2-3 and ES1-1-1 showed low tolerance for cold at the seedling stage and flowered earlier than the check variety IR50. Both lines had similar seedling height and leaf number at 55 DAS; number of tillers/plant at harvest was lower than that of IR50 (see table).

Two hill rice varieties introduced from Bhutan, MAAP and KAAP, showed high seedling tolerance for cold, and flowered earliest. But number of tillers/plant was very low. Khonorullo, another hill rice, showed cold

susceptibility at all growth stages, with delayed heading. CB-1 (Chinsurah Boro-1) exhibited high seedling tolerance for cold but flowered late. Awned and red grains also restrict CB-1 use.

Varieties that flowered around mid-Mar in West Bengal usually experience temperatures of 22-25 °C during panicle development and produce a higher percentage of filled spikelets/panicle. Using the Bhutanese varieties that flower between 17-19 Mar in the hybridization program may provide plants that flower early, with cold tolerance at both seedling and reproductive stages, suitable for dry season (boro) rice in West Bengal. □

Characters related to cold tolerance at different growth stages. ^a West Bengal, India, 1984-85.

Genotype	Source	Leaf yellowing ^a			Seedling ht (cm)			Leaf no. ^a			Tillers (no./plant)	Days to heading
		25 DAS	45 DAS	55 DAS	25 DAS	45 DAS	55 DAS	25 DAS	45 DAS	55 DAS		
<i>New lines</i>												
IR9262-5-2-2-2	IRRI	5	7	7	6	8	10	3	3	4	10	125
IR15579-135-3	IRRI	3	5	5	7	9	12	3	4	5	9	125
IR7167-33-2-4-2-3	IRRI	5	7	7	6	8	9	3	3	5	9	131
IR13155-60-3-1	IRRI	5	7	7	6	9	12	3	3	5	10	127
IR5716-18-1	IRRI	5	5	5	7	8	10	3	4	5	9	127
IR8866-30-3-1-4-2	IRRI	5	7	7	6	8	10	3	4	4	9	131
ES1-2-3	India	3	5	5	5	9	10	3	4	4	6	117
ES1-1-1	India	5	5	5	5	9	10	3	4	4	7	118
IR50	IRRI	5	7	9	6	8	9	3	4	5	10	129
<i>Hill rice</i>												
MAAP	Bhutan	1	1	1	10	12	15	3	4	5	3	115
KAAP	Bhutan	1	5	7	8	12	16	3	4	5	4	113
Khonorullo	Bhutan	5	7	7	6	9	11	3	4	5	7	131
<i>Local check</i>												
CB-1	India	1	1	1	12	15	20	3	4	5	13	139
Average diurnal temp (°C)		20	19	18								

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale.

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